

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1: Pigment production on King A medium agar plate and antibiotic susceptibility behavior. (A) *P. aeruginosa* clinical strain on agar plates showing yellow (a) and green (b) coloration. Disc diffusion on Mueller Hinton agar displayed antibiotic susceptibility of green (B) and yellow (C) pigment producing clinical strains.

Negative Control

No Pigment

Green Pigment

Yellow Pigment

Supplementary Figure 2: Representative images of Rapidec Carba NP test for MBL producing *P. aeruginosa* clinical strain. The reaction's positivity must be read in well 'e' while well 'd' is a control that must be red to validate the test. Yellow color in well "e" represents strong positive result for MBL producers (indicated by solid arrow). Weak MBL producers are represented by orange, light orange, dark orange color in obtained in well "e" (indicated by dotted arrow). Red color in well "e" indicates MBL negative isolate. We identified yellow pigment producing strains were primarily strong MBL producers compared followed by green and no-pigment producing strains.

Supplementary Figure 3: EtBr Cartwheel assay for drug efflux activity determination. Fluorescence of *P. aeruginosa* strains on agar plates containing EtBr (2mg/L). Image showing yellow pigment producing strain have enhanced efflux activity (reduced fluorescence) where non-pigmented strain have low efflux activity (high fluorescence). ATCC 25923 strain was used as negative control for efflux activity.

Supplementary Figure 4: Mucooid and non-mucooid behavior for biofilm and antibiotic susceptibility. (A) Biofilm forming mucooid and non-mucooid *P. aeruginosa* clinical strain (shown in %). (B) Difference in resistance pattern (%) for mucooid and non-mucooid strains. (C) Difference in resistance pattern (%) for biofilm producers and non-biofilm producers. # Difference of more than 15% of resistance between groups.

Supplementary Table 1: MIC of MBL positive yellow, green and no pigment producing *P. aeruginosa* clinical strains. CSLI breakpoint was determined using reference strain ATCC 27853.

Antibiotics	MBL Positive bacterial strains.									
	Yellow					No Pigment		Green		CLSI BP
	PA103	PA363	PA978	PA786	PA769	PA302	PA407	PA899	PA015	
Cefepime	64.0	64.0	128.0	64.0	128.0	64.0	64.0	128.0	64.00	≥32
Netilmicin	64.0	128.0	64.0	128.0	128.0	32.0	64.0	64.0	32.00	≥32
Gentamicin	128.0	128.0	128.0	128.0	64.0	32.0	32.0	64.0	16.00	≥16
Ciprofloxacin	32.0	32.0	16.0	64.0	32.0	8.0	16.0	16.0	0.25	≥2
Imipenem	64.0	128.0	64.0	32.0	16.0	128.0	32.0	32.0	32.00	≥8
Aztreonam	128.0	128.0	64.0	128.0	128.0	32.0	128.0	64.0	128.00	≥32
Ceftazidime	64.0	128.0	128.0	64.0	128.0	64.0	64.0	64.0	64.00	≥32